

Mixoplankton and a new paradigm for ecology in coastal and marine waters

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<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/natural-capital-and-ecosystem-assessment-programme>

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Mixoplankton and a new paradigm for ecology in coastal and marine waters

Ecology under the traditional paradigm

The traditional paradigm viewed marine systems akin to terrestrial ecosystems, with the growth of phytoplankton considered to be plant-like, controlled by inorganic nutrients.

Ecology under the mixoplankton paradigm

New science shows that many so-called 'phytoplankton' can eat as well as use nutrients. In addition, many 'protist zooplankton' can photosynthesize. Collectively these organisms that can simultaneously photosynthesize and eat are the **mixoplankton**.

Most **mixoplankton** populations contribute positively to biodiversity and fisheries. However, some are notable Harmful Algal species.

Briefing on how mixoplankton affect ocean health, fish and aquaculture

Read more about marine 'killer triffids'

Importance of mixoplankton paradigm in the United Nation's Plankton Manifesto

What are mixoplankton?

Mixoplankton are single-celled organisms. They use dissolved organic and inorganic nutrients, perform photosynthesis (like plants) and hunt for food (like animals). They exploit these processes together for competitive advantage.

Small organisms with big impact

Mixoplankton range in size from one-tenth to 10 times human hair thickness (human hair diameter = 0.065 mm = 65 µm).

Activities range from supporting fisheries to killing fisheries and from consuming CO₂ to making O₂. The White Cliffs of Dover are made from the remnants of some mixoplankton.

Emiliana

Measures less than one-tenth of the diameter of human hair. Sequesters CO₂ and makes limestone and chalk (e.g., White Cliffs of Dover)

Heterosigma

Measures one-fifth the diameter of a human hair. *Heterosigma* blooms kill fish.

Dinophysis

Measures two-thirds the diameter of a human hair. *Dinophysis* blooms lead to closures of shell fisheries due to toxicity.

Laboea

The same diameter as a human hair.

Tripos

3 times the diameter of a human hair.

Laboea, *Tripos* and various other mixoplankton support biodiversity, ocean health and fisheries.

Mixoplankton – a new paradigm demanding new monitoring approaches for coastal and marine waters

Traditional sampling tools

Traditional approaches assume phytoplankton growth (akin to green plants) is limited by light and inorganic nutrients.

Recommendations: additional sampling tools

The new **mixoplankton** paradigm forces us to develop new approaches to monitoring because these organisms have a complex role in the food-web as producers and consumers.

Human activities and the **mixoplankton** paradigm

Traditional management of nutrient releases (e.g., from farm, sewage, industries) need reappraisal.

Hydrological and coastal engineering can lead to changes in water flows, turbulence and salinity. Such changes may affect the structuring of plankton communities including **mixoplankton** growths (some of which could be HABs).

In sewage treatments, nitrogen (N) removal needs to be improved, aligning it with advances made in phosphorus (P) removal. This will prevent extreme N:P ratios that affect **mixoplankton** growth and HABs.

Excessive dissolved organic matter (DOM) from silage and sewage affects **mixoplankton** growth. Release of DOM needs reappraisal and regulation.

Various **mixoplankton** species have long-lasting viable resting stages (cysts). Dredging and allied activities may lead to resuspension of cysts and also release of nutrients. Benthic surveys would allay concerns of the promotion of **mixoplankton** HABs at sites of dredging and of spoil disposal.

Recommendation:

Mixoplankton need appropriate recognition and explicit inclusion within monitoring and management of the UK marine systems. It is important to appreciate the differences between phytoplankton and **mixoplankton** and reflect these in the ways that risk assessments and monitoring of the environment are undertaken.

Climate change and the mixoplankton paradigm

Climate change will see increased variation in weather: more extreme storms, heat waves, flooding. These will impact plankton diversity, inevitably including changes to **mixoplankton** populations. Some changes will impact food-chains leading to fisheries. Some may affect the risk of HABs.

Excess rainfall and flooding can overwhelm wastewater infrastructure, exacerbate runoff from farms, bringing organic as well as inorganic nutrients into coastal waters; these can affect growth of **mixoplankton** and also of their prey organisms.

Our seas and coasts are rapidly changing due to climate change and human interventions. Changes in nutrients, waterflow and temperature can change the balance of 'good' and 'bad' **mixoplankton** at both local and regional scales.

'Good' **mixoplankton** support UK natural capital. Any loss of these **mixoplankton** with climate change may be as deleterious as promoting 'bad' (HAB) **mixoplankton**.

Recommendations:

- The risks of the loss of 'good' **mixoplankton**, supporting UK natural capital, and/or promotion of noxious or HAB **mixoplankton**, need to be considered when updating the climate change risk register.
- All policy and guidance documentation concerning 'phytoplankton' require review as many phytoplankton are actually **mixoplankton** with different physiologies and ecologies.